

Yashil

IQTISODIYOT va TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, siyosiy, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

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THE CONTRIBUTION OF TRANSPORT IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF TOURISM INDUSTRY (CASE STUDY: UZBEKISTAN)

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Abstract: This article examines the various functions that transportation plays in the tourism industry, focusing on how it not only makes it easier to go to places physically but also makes a substantial contribution to the sociocultural and economic advancement of popular tourist areas.

Key words: tourism, transport industry, Uzbekistan, travel behavior, air travel.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada transportning turizm sanoatida bajaradigan turli funktsiyalari ko'rib chiqiladi va u nafaqat joylarga borishni osonlashtirishi, balki mashhur turistik hududlarning ijtimoiy-madaniy va iqtisodiy rivojlanishiga sezilarli hissa qo'shishiga qaratilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: turizm, transport sanoati, O'zbekiston, sayohat xatti-harakati, havo sayohati.

Аннотация: В этой статье рассматриваются различные функции, которые транспорт играет в индустрии туризма, уделяя особое внимание тому, как он не только облегчает физическое перемещение в места, но и вносит существенный вклад в социокультурное и экономическое развитие популярных туристических районов.

Ключевые слова: туризм, транспортная отрасль, Узбекистан, туристическое поведение, авиаперелеты.

INTRODUCTION

Tourism is widely recognized as a key driver of economic growth and socio-cultural exchange. At the heart of this dynamic industry lies transportation, an essential component that interlinks destinations with markets and cultures across the globe. The aim of this research is to delve into the multifaceted role of transport within the tourism sector, examining how it not only facilitates access to and from destinations but also enhances the overall tourist experience, contributes to economic development, and supports sustainable travel practices.

Transportation's influence on tourism is profound and pervasive, shaping everything from the initial decision of a tourist to visit a destination to their satisfaction and subsequent choices. Whether by air, land, or sea, transport systems enable the very possibility of tourism, allowing people to explore new landscapes, immerse in different cultures, and partake in local economies. Moreover, as the world increasingly prioritizes sustainability, the transport sector faces pressing challenges and opportunities to innovate and minimize its environmental footprint while continuing to support tourism growth. It is fact that, tourism is an indispensable component of the global economy.

Research indicates that tourists typically allocate 30 to 40 percent of their total vacation budget to transportation, with the remainder spent on accommodations, food, and other activities, underscoring the critical role of transport in tourism economics (SANTACO, 2023). Industry revenues are expected to reach an historic high of \$964 billion in 2024. An inventory of 40.1 million flights is expected to be available in 2024, exceeding the 2019 level of 38.9 million and up from the 36.8 million flights expected in 2023 (IATA, 2023). Tourism's contribution to economic stability extends to numerous countries, including Uzbekistan, which welcomed 6.6 million tourists in 2023. (Kun.uz, 2024) This influx underscores the sector's vital role in Uzbekistan's economy, highlighting tourism's potential to drive economic growth and cultural exchange on both a local and global scale.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Most utility trips occur regularly and typically within the traveler’s local or broader residential area. According to the World Tourism Organization (2019), tourism-related trips involve travel beyond one’s usual environment. These trips often include seasonal, one-time, or solo journeys, leaving travelers unfamiliar with local transportation systems and options. Today, there is a pressing need for modes of transport that are safe, convenient, and affordable for travelers. The scientists provided the classification of the transport modes which is given in the following figure (fig. 1). To some extent, the choice of transportation for travel can be influenced by individual factors such as financial means, time constraints, and personal preferences. Attractions or destinations seeking to draw visitors from distant locations have significant considerations to make. Travel modes between starting points and destinations can include a wide array of options like bicycles, horses, cars, buses, trains, ships, and planes. In many parts of the world, cars and air travel are the predominant modes, though this is not always the case.

Pic.1: Classification of transport modes

Tourist journeys often involve multiple forms of transport such buses, planes or combination of them. Conversely, many domestic vacations undertaken by families might only utilize one type of transport, such as a car. The selection of transportation is crucial not only for the convenience and preferences of the traveler but also for its impacts on both the origin and destination areas. The decision for choosing a certain transport mode is made according to:

Tab. 1: Essential factors while choosing transport by the tourists

Consideration	Details
1. Cost	Public Transport, Trains, Buses, Air Travel
2. Comfort and convenience	Seating, Amenities, Punctuality, Ease of Use
3. Travel time	Duration, Speed
4. Accessibility	Connectivity, Direct Routes
5. Safety and reliability	Safety Record, Reliability, Regularity
6. Nature of trip	Purpose, Group Size, Duration, Luggage
7. Flexibility	Self-Driven Cars, Rental Vehicles

It is clear that countries with well-developed transport infrastructure tend to attract more international tourists. For example, in 2023, the USA generated over \$190 billion in tourism receipts, followed by China with \$154 billion, and Canada with \$16 billion. This correlation highlights the importance of efficient and accessible transportation systems in boosting a country’s appeal to international visitors (Yam Chhetri, 2023). Taleb Rifai (2017) said that Sustainable transport and mobility are essential for the future of tourism. Prideaux (2010) echoes this by stating that in the context of tourism, transport is primarily functional, and the level of satisfaction or utility it provides is tied to time, which acts as a proxy for cost. This is interpreted as an implied demand where the travel mode contributes little intrinsic environmental value to the tourism experience.

Turning to the Uzbekistan, it is actively engaged in the global transport framework, being a member of nine international conventions and two international organizations that govern road transport. Additionally, the country has established bilateral intergovernmental transport agreements with 26 countries across Europe, Asia, and the CIS. The population is actively using cars as the main mode of transportation for their personal reasons while public transport is used less and is applied only for almost 19% (Numbeo, 2024). This clearly shows that public transport must be developed which will result in the wider usage by not only the locals but also foreigners.

Pic. 2: Statistics on the usage of different modes of transport in Uzbekistan

According to NUMBEO (2024), each passenger produces approximately 620.84kg of CO2 annually as a result of commuting to work or school. To counterbalance this carbon emission, it would require approximately 28.52 trees per passenger to produce enough oxygen. The total number of air passengers in Uzbekistan is projected to be 2.38 million in 2024. While the total number of registered carrier departures in Uzbekistan is forecast to amount to 16.24k inhabitants in 2024 (Statista, 2024). According to the Statistics Agency of the Republic of Uzbekistan (2023), the length of public roads in Uzbekistan is almost 43 thousand km resulting in fourth place in the CIS in terms of the indicator. Besides that, Uzbekistan and Italy will launch a luxury train for foreign tourists through the ancient cities of the republic. This will be the first global scale project in Central Asia. Its launch is scheduled for the end of 2026 (Podrobno.uz, 2024).

As a result of analyzing data for the spring tourist season (from January to May), it was determined that out of 2,589.2 thousand foreign citizens who visited Uzbekistan, those who arrived by air amounted to 428.4 thousand people (16.5%), by rail - 32, 8 thousand people (1.3%), road transport - 18.4 thousand people (0.7%). The largest number were hikers - 2,109.6 thousand people (81.5%) (the Statistics Agency of the Republic of Uzbekistan, 2023). According to the Statistics Agency, in January-March 2024, 63.8 million passengers were transported in the Tashkent metro.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

To achieve the research objectives, a quantitative approach was used. The quantitative research method includes the usage of the secondary data (a review of the literature on transport and tourism development) and semi-structured interview. The literature review included a broad overview of the theories and ideas pertaining to the transport, the tourism industry, as well as the elements that either help or hinder the growth in the hospitality industry. This aided in a better understanding of the study’s context and provided information for the analysis of the data gathered.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

The results of the secondary data showed the lack and problems of the public transport. There is the research that was conducted by independent journalist in Tashkent. We can use this research as the main resource of the analysis because the public transport of Tashkent is the leading one among the regions of Uzbekistan. The problems found in this area can be generalized to other cities as well. It must be said that a small part of the respondents was satisfied with everything, according to them, nothing needs to be improved. However, majority of the respondents indicated following complaints about the usage of public transport such as:

Table 1: Problems with the transport (in the case of Uzbekistan)

Problems	Description	Results
1. Problems of congestion	Buses and subways are often crowded especially during rush hours	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> discomfort, increases the risk of disease and transmission of infections
2. Stiffness in the subway	Lack of air conditioning in the subway cabs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Cases of fainting
3. Lack of air conditioning in the old buses	It is usually hot in the old buses	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Cases of fainting Overheat
4. Insufficient number of vehicles	insufficient public transport and overcrowded routes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Crush in transport Long stops
5. Long delays at stops	Buses stop more than it is needed	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> late for the work, study buses get crowded because there are not enough of them

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

In conclusion, transport is indispensable for the tourism sector, yet it poses significant challenges, particularly regarding environmental degradation and the sustainability of tourism practices. Our analysis highlights the advantages and disadvantages of air and road transport, which dominate tourist travel. Key factors that tourists should consider when choosing transportation modes were discussed in detail. Additionally, we examined the transport services in Uzbekistan, assessing both their achievements and shortcomings within the tourism industry. Insights were gathered from tourists and tour agencies, leading to informed conclusions about the role and impact of different transport types in tourism. Effectively addressing these impacts can promote the development of more sustainable, economically viable and socially responsible tourism practices. The solutions and recommendations consist of:

Strategic policy development	Governments should formulate and implement policies that promote sustainable transportation infrastructure, such as encouraging the use of electric buses or scooters in tourist areas
Regulatory controls	Establish rules to limit the number of visitors to environmentally sensitive areas to avoid overtourism and its associated negative impacts
Adopt green technologies	Encourage transportation companies to adopt sustainable technologies such as electric or hybrid engines to significantly reduce carbon emissions
Expanded service offerings	development of new services for the growing market of environmentally conscious travelers, such as eco-friendly transportation to major tourist attractions.
Operational adjustments	review of operating methods to improve efficiency and reduce environmental impact, such as optimizing route planning to minimize fuel consumption
Sustainable practices	Integrate sustainability into business models by offering packages that include environmentally friendly transportation options
Educational proposals	develop courses and programs focused on tourism and sustainable transportation to prepare future leaders in these fields

The users of the transport including both foreign and local passengers found out some drawbacks of the transport system. To tackle the problems, the government must promote green alternatives and encourage the use of e-cars. Another idea would be the introduction of the special app that displays real-time schedules for various types of transportation, increasing schedule accuracy. To make the travel more pleasant and comfortable for the tourists, it is advised to limit the airline monopoly and increase the tourism potential of Uzbekistan, reduce the monopoly of the national airline Uzbekistan Airways. The emergence of competing companies will reduce prices and offer citizens more affordable and comfortable travel options. By adopting these strategies, Uzbekistan can enhance its tourism sector's sustainability, efficiency, and overall appeal.

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